

REVIEW OF FAIR AND EQUITABLE TREATMENT STANDARD IN THE CONTEXT OF CENTRAL ASIA

Toshtemirova Nafosat Rahimovna

ntoshtemirova@gmail.com

master's degree student at the University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Abstract

The Fair and Equitable Treatment (FET) standard is one of the most significant and frequently invoked protections in international investment law. Despite its widespread application in bilateral investment treaties (BITs), the interpretation and scope of the FET standard remain controversial due to the absence of a universally accepted definition. This article examines the evolution of the FET standard, its interpretation in investment treaty arbitration, and the challenges associated with its application. Particular attention is given to the legal frameworks of the Central Asian states and the extent to which their investment treaties incorporate and define the FET obligation. It further assesses the implications of these developments for balancing investor protection with the host States' regulatory autonomy. The study concludes by identifying key challenges facing Central Asian countries in the implementation of the FET standard and offers recommendations for future treaty reforms.

Keywords

Fair and Equitable Treatment (FET), international investment law, bilateral investment treaties (BITs), investment arbitration, Central Asia, investor protection, treaty reform, regulatory autonomy, sustainable investment.

Annotatsiya. *Adolatli va teng munosabat (Fair and Equitable Treatment - FET) standarti xalqaro investitsiya huquqidagi eng muhim va investitsiya nizolarida eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan investorlarni himoya qilish standartlaridan biridir. Ikki tomonlama investitsiya bitimlarida (BIT) keng qo'llanilishiga qaramay, FET standartining talqini va qo'llanish doirasi uning umum e'tirof etilgan yagona ta'rifi mavjud emasligi sababli hanuzgacha bahsli masala bo'lib qolmoqda. Ushbu maqolada FET standartining rivojlanishi, investitsiya shartnomalari arbitrajidagi talqini hamda uni qo'llash bilan bog'liq muammolar tahlil qilinadi. Alohida e'tibor Markaziy Osiyo*

davlatlarining huquqiy bazasiga hamda ularning investitsiya bitimlarida FET majburiyatining qanday aks ettirilgani va belgilanganiga qaratilgan. Shuningdek, maqolada mazkur rivojlanishlarning investorlarni himoya qilish va mezbondavlatlarning tartibga solish vakolatlari o‘rtasidagi muvozanatni ta’minlashga ta’siri baholanadi. Tadqiqot yakunida Markaziy Osiyo davlatlarida FET standartini qo‘llash bilan bog‘liq asosiy muammolar aniqlanib, kelgusidagi shartnomaviy islohotlar bo‘yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi.

Tayanch so‘zlar: *adolatli va teng munosabat (FET), xalqaro investitsiya huquqi, ikki tomonlama investitsiya bitimlari (BIT), investitsiya arbitraji, Markaziy Osiyo, investorlarni himoya qilish, shartnomaviy islohotlar, davlatning tartibga solish vakolati, barqaror investitsiyalar.*

Introduction

This article analyses the Fair and Equitable Treatment (FET) standard in the context of Central Asia. It first examines the scope of FET and its application in investor-state dispute settlement (ISDS) more generally. It then turns to the bilateral investment treaties (BITs) concluded by Central Asian states in order to assess the precise wording, analysis, interpretation, and application of the FET standard. On the basis of this survey, it explains why the predominance of broad, unqualified FET clauses in the region is problematic for the host states concerned. The article further reviews current treaty-drafting practices regarding FET clauses in model BITs and, on that basis, proposes recommendations for a model FET clause for use by Central Asian countries.

Fair and equitable treatment

Most international investment agreements (IIA), including bilateral investment treaties (BIT) provide for fair and equitable treatment of investors. According to this standard, the host state of investments is obliged to create a fair and equitable environment for foreign investment. Most IIAs provide for FET wording akin to the below:

“Investments of nationals or companies of each Contracting Party shall at all times be accorded fair and equitable treatment and shall enjoy full protection and security in the territory of the other Contracting Party. Neither Contracting Party shall in any way impair by unreasonable or discriminatory measures the management,

maintenance, use, enjoyment or disposal of investments in its territory of nationals or companies of the other Contracting Party. Each Contracting Party shall observe any obligation it may have entered into with regard to investments of nationals or companies of the other Contracting Party.”¹

As noted that the two concepts of ‘fair’ and of ‘equitable’ are not to be taken as distinct elements to be applied separately. The general assumption is that ‘fair and equitable’ represent a single, unified standard.²

As shown further in the article below, the treaty-drafting practices and analysis of investor-state dispute settlement reveal that the contours of fair and equitable treatment remain ill-defined, its precise content underdeveloped and what accounts for the breach of FET standard disputed. What is generally accepted though is that FET is an absolute standard and it does not require comparison to the treatment afforded other investors. As a result, the interpretation and application of FET turn heavily on the facts of each case. As noted, FET is a flexible, elastic standard whose normative content is being expanded to include new elements. Because of this, it is the most often invoked treaty standard in investor-state arbitration, present in almost every single claim brought by foreign investors against host states.³ In terms of statistics, at the time of writing, as of 16 June 2026, the UNCTAD Investment Dispute Settlement Navigator lists 673 investor-state disputes in which the breach of FET standard is invoked and in 225 out of these 673 cases, the tribunal has actually decided that the breach of FET standard occurred.⁴

Investment tribunals have since given detailed content to the meaning of the standard. They have applied it to a broad range of circumstances and have given it meaning

¹ The United Kingdom Model BIT 2008, Article 2(2). Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements/treaty-files/2847/download>

² Dolzer, Kriebaum and Schreuer, Principles of International Investment Law. 3rd Edition, Oxford University Press, 2022 – p.190

³ Yannaca-Small, Katia. Fair and Equitable Treatment. Have its contours fully developed? Yannaca-Small, Katia (ed.), Arbitration Under International Investment Agreements: A Guide to the Key Issues, 2nd Edition, Oxford University Press, 2018 – p.501

⁴ UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, Investment Dispute Settlement Navigator. Available by advanced search at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/investment-dispute-settlement/advanced-search>
<https://www.europa-revue.com/index.php/eur>

through their practice.⁵

Among situations giving rise to a violation of the FET standard, tribunals identified:

- a. Lack of respect for the obligation of vigilance and protection
- b. Denial of due process or denial of justice. Notably, several tribunals cited lack of judicial or procedural propriety as evidence of fair and equitable treatment violation;
- c. Non-observance or frustration of investors' legitimate expectations;
- d. Coercion and harassment by the organs of a host State;
- e. Failure to offer a stable and predictable legal framework;
- f. Unjust enrichment;
- g. Evidence of bad faith. Several tribunals, however, noted that bad faith is not required to prove a violation of FET;
- h. Absence of transparency;
- i. Arbitrary and discriminatory treatment.⁶

For example, the above-cited United Kingdom Model BIT mentions that the host state should not take unreasonable or discriminatory measures in regard to foreign investments and not breach any obligation the state may have entered into with regard to investments. As stated herein the UK Model BIT determines two elements of FET. But the question remains open whether the FET scope is limited to these two elements or can go beyond what is mentioned specifically.

The FET clause in IIAs and BITs of Central Asia

In terms of statistics, at the time of writing, as of 16 June 2026, the UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub lists a total of 2,864 IIAs worldwide, of which 2237 are currently in force. Out of these 2,864, the content of 2823 IIAs is mapped. What is noteworthy is that 2019 of the 2823 IIAs contain a FET clause which is not qualified, and do not provide for definition of what accounts for FET, the other 150 do not provide for any kind of FET standard, and in the other 649 IIAs, FET is qualified.⁷

⁵ Dolzer, Kriebaum and Schreuer. Principles of International Investment Law. 3rd Edition, Oxford University Press, 2022 – p.187

⁶ Ugale Anastasiya, Knoll-Tudor Ioana. Fair and Equitable Treatment. Available at: <https://jusmundi.com/en/document/publication/en-fair-and-equitable-treatment>
<https://www.europa-revue.com/index.php/eur>

With respect to the treaty practice of Central Asia, as of June 2026, 231 BITs involving Central Asian states are recorded in the UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, with 175 being in force: Kyrgyzstan has concluded 40 BITs, with 27 being in force, Kazakhstan 56, with 45 being in force, Uzbekistan 59, with 50 being in force, Turkmenistan 31, with 25 being in force, Tajikistan 45, with 28 being in force. These treaties constitute the primary legal framework governing the protection of foreign investors and investments in the region.

According to the UNCTAD Policy Hub, the content of the 123 BITs of Central Asian countries is mapped, including the 12 terminated BITs. Only 25 of these 123 BITs contain a qualified FET provision, the other 9 do not contain any FET provision.

The author of the article conducted the full analysis of the FET clauses found in the BITs of Central Asia,⁸ and grouped them by country. Of the 51 BITs of Uzbekistan surveyed, 48 contain an operative FET (or FET-equivalent) obligation, while 3 do not. Among the 48 treaties that do impose an FET obligation, the drafting falls into three patterns. The large majority, to be specific 40 treaties, frame the FET standard in unqualified, autonomous terms, leaving its content to be determined by tribunals without reference to any external benchmark. A second group of 6 qualifies the standard by tying it to international law or the minimum standard of treatment (Belgium-Luxembourg, Finland, France, Kuwait, Sweden, and the United States), thereby constraining its autonomous expansion. A third group of 2 qualifies the standard instead through an enumerated list of constituent elements, China (2011), and India (2024), the latter relying on a closed customary international law list rather than employing the term “FET” at all. The overwhelming predominance of unqualified clauses is the central feature of this treaty landscape, and it is the principal concern the model clause proposed below seeks to address.

Of the 22 BITs of Turkmenistan surveyed, 19 contain an FET (or FET-equivalent) obligation, 1 is indeterminate (the Israel treaty which does not contain any article on

⁷ UNCTAD Investment Policy Hub, International Investment Agreements Navigator, IIA Content Mapping. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements/iaa-mapping/Content>

⁸ The author of the article used all the available text of BITs from Electronic Database of Investment treaties. Available by country search at: <https://edit.wti.org/document/investment-treaty/search>

standards of treatment), and 2 do not operate as FET guarantees: the Azerbaijan-Turkmenistan 2018 treaty, which contains no FET provision at all, and the Turkey-Turkmenistan 1992 treaty, in which FET appears only in the preamble. Among the 19 treaties that impose an FET obligation, 16 frame the standard in unqualified, autonomous terms, 1 qualifies it by reference to the principles of international law (the France-Turkmenistan BIT 1994) and 2 qualify it through an enumerated list of elements: The Hungary-Turkmenistan BIT 2023, and the Kazakhstan-Turkmenistan BIT 2024. In the Kazakhstan-Turkmenistan BIT 2024, the FET provision contains an exhaustive list of elements and is tied to the minimum standard of treatment under customary international law. What is noteworthy is that no Turkmenistan BIT contains a genuinely standalone FET provision and wherever FET in the BITs signed by Turkmenistan appears, it is paired with at least MFN treatment, and usually with full protection and security (FPS) and national treatment (NT) as well.

Of the 33 BITs of Tajikistan surveyed, 28 contain an FET (or FET-equivalent) obligation, while 5 do not contain any provision on FET standard. Among the 28 instruments that do impose an FET obligation, the 24 BITs frame the standard in unqualified, autonomous terms, the 2 BITs qualify it by reference to international law or the minimum standard of treatment (the BITs with France dated 2002, and with Japan dated 2025, and the 2 BITs qualify it through an enumerated, customary international law based element (the BITs signed by China dated 2024, and with Pakistan dated 2004), each defining FET by reference to the denial of justice and due process standard.

Of the 34 BITs of Kyrgyzstan surveyed, the 33 BITs contain an FET (or FET-equivalent) obligation, while only 1 the Armenia-Kyrgyzstan BIT does not provide any FET obligation with a general guarantee of “protection”. Among the 33 treaties that impose an FET obligation, the 24 BITs frame the standard in unqualified, autonomous terms, the 7 BITs qualify it by reference to international law or the minimum standard of treatment (Finland, France, Georgia (2016), Kazakhstan (2024), Sweden, Turkey, and the United States) and the 2 BITs qualify it through an enumerated list of elements (Hungary (2020), and India (2019), which relies on a closed customary international

law list rather than the term “FET” itself.

Most Kazakhstan BITs articulate FET and full protection and security together within a single sentence (21 treaties). A distinct cluster, by contrast, subsumes the “fair and equitable” formulation within the no-less-favourable (national and most-favoured-nation) standard rather than stating FET as an autonomous obligation (Romania, Spain, Switzerland, and Uzbekistan). A further five treaties articulate FET twice over, once in conjunction with full protection and security, and once fused with the relative NT/MFN standard (Azerbaijan, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Malaysia, and Ukraine). The four most recent and most carefully drafted treaties (Singapore, 2018; Qatar, 2022; Kyrgyzstan, 2024; and Turkmenistan, 2024) tie FET to the minimum standard of treatment under customary international law and define its content through an enumerated list of elements.

The research conducted above has shown five drafting variations of FET standard found in the BITs of Central Asia:

- i. BITs that make no reference to the FET;
- ii. BITs that make reference to the FET or its elements in the preamble only;
- iii. BITs that mention FET alone;
- iv. BITs that mention FET together with other standards of treatment, MFN, NT and FPS;
- v. BITs which refer to FET in conjunction with an indicative/exhaustive list of FET constitutive elements.

The FET standard in selected BITs of Central Asia

The FET standard when it is included into BITs of Central Asia is mostly found in the main text of the respective BITs. Occasionally, mentioning of “fair and equitable treatment” is found in preambles of the BITs. For example, the Uzbekistan-Jordan 2025 BIT (not in force) states in the preamble that:

“...and agreeing that fair and equitable treatment of investments is desirable in order to maintain a stable investment framework, which will contribute to the optimal use of

economic resources and the improvement of living standards.”⁹

The Uzbekistan-Sweden 2001 BIT states in the preamble that:

“...desiring to intensify economic cooperation to the mutual benefit of both countries and to maintain fair and equitable conditions for investments by investors of one Contracting Party in the territory of the other Contracting Party.”¹⁰

Interestingly, the above-mentioned BITs contain an independent provision on FET standard, apart from “desirable fair and equitable conditions for investments” mentioned in the preamble. However, there are several BITs with mentioning of “fair and equitable treatment” in the preamble without a standalone, independent clause on FET standard in the main text of treaties. For example, the 1992 Turkmenistan-Turkey BIT mentions in the preamble that “...fair and equitable treatment of investment is desirable...”¹¹ but does not contain any provision on FET standard in the main text. The 1996 Tajikistan-Turkey BIT,¹² the 2007 Tajikistan-Azerbaijan BIT,¹³ the 1992 Kazakhstan-Turkey BIT¹⁴ also do mention a FET standard in the preamble only and do not provide for a FET standard further. Thus, it remains unclear whether the contracting parties of these BITs aimed to provide for fair and equitable treatment standard for foreign investments as it is noted by an author that “...preambles emphasising the parties’ aim to create a stable framework for investment may be interpreted by arbitral tribunals in favour of investors in case of interpretative uncertainties”.¹⁵

Several of the BITs provide for a FET standard neither in the preamble nor in the main text of treaties, for example the 1992 Uzbekistan-Egypt BIT, the 2009 Uzbekistan-

⁹ The Uzbekistan-Jordan 2025 BIT. Available at: <https://edit.wti.org/document/show/7587503e-b42d-482a-8fe7-46d001b28543>

¹⁰ The Uzbekistan-Sweden 2001 BIT. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements/treaty-files/2309/download>

¹¹ The 1992 Turkmenistan-Turkey BIT. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements/treaty-files/4785/download>

¹² The 1996 Tajikistan-Turkey BIT. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements/treaty-files/2339/download>

¹³ The 2007 Tajikistan-Azerbaijan BIT. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements/treaty-files/4663/download>

¹⁴ The 1992 Kazakhstan-Turkey BIT. Available at: <https://investmentpolicy.unctad.org/international-investment-agreements/treaty-files/1789/download>

¹⁵ Ioana Knoll-Tudor. Fair and Equitable Treatment in the Context of Central Asian Cases. Kiran N. Gore, Elijah Putilin, et al. (eds). International Investment Law and Investor-State Disputes in Central Asia: Emerging Issues, Kluwer Law International, 2022 - pp. 244

Bahrain BIT, the 2018 Turkmenistan-Azerbaijan BIT, the 2011 Tajikistan-Qatar BIT, the 2001 Tajikistan-Ukraine BIT, the 1994 Kyrgyzstan-Armenia BIT, the 1995 Kazakhstan-Israel BIT, the 2018 Kazakhstan-United Arab Emirates BIT. Several of the BITs do not contain any standalone FET standard but prohibit states from taking “arbitrary or discriminatory” measures that limit the “management, maintenance, use, enjoyment or disposal of investments”. For example, above mentioned the 2018 Turkmenistan-Azerbaijan BIT states in Article 2(3) that “Neither Contracting Party shall allow compulsory, unreasonable or biased actions in respect of the development, operation, management, ownership, placement or other disposition of investments of investors of the other Contracting Party in the territory of its State.” “...The 2012 UNCTAD Report notes that arbitrariness, unreasonableness and discrimination are in any case intrinsic to the FET, such that the explicit reference to these prohibitions in a FET clause does not advance the understanding of the FET scope, which goes beyond such prohibitions.”¹⁶ It follows that the inclusion of one or several elements of FET standard into an IIA without a full independent clause is not to be construed as the inclusion of a full-fledged FET standard.

Where a treaty clause expressly links the FET standard to NT and/or MFN treatment by requiring, for instance, that fair and equitable treatment be “not less favourable” than that accorded to national or third-State investors, as in Article 3(2) of the Kazakhstan-Romania BIT (2010), the NT and MFN levels operate as a floor that raises the minimum content of FET, thereby affording investors potentially higher protection. By contrast, where the three standards merely coexist within the same provision without any causal or comparative connection, as in the Kazakhstan-Netherlands BIT (2002), their juxtaposition has no bearing on the interpretation of the FET obligation, which retains its autonomous meaning.¹⁷

There are BITs which qualify FET to some extent. They can be classified into two groups: 1) FET qualified with reference to customary international law and/or

¹⁶ Ioana Knoll-Tudor. Fair and Equitable Treatment in the Context of Central Asian Cases. Kiran N. Gore, Elijah Putilin, et al. (eds). *International Investment Law and Investor-State Disputes in Central Asia: Emerging Issues*, Kluwer Law International, 2022 - pp. 244

¹⁷ Ioana Knoll-Tudor. Fair and Equitable Treatment in the Context of Central Asian Cases. Kiran N. Gore, Elijah Putilin, et al. (eds). *International Investment Law and Investor-State Disputes in Central Asia: Emerging Issues*, Kluwer Law International, 2022 - pp. 250-251

minimum standard of treatment; and 2) FET qualified with inclusion of exhaustive list of what accounts for violation of FET. In regard to the first group, the FET standard qualified with reference to customary international law and/or minimum standard of treatment is mostly concluded during the period from the 1990s till roughly the 2010s.¹⁸ In regard to the second group, the FET standard qualified with an exhaustive or non-exhaustive list can mostly be found in the BITs signed after the 2010s.¹⁹ For example, the 2023 Turkmenistan-Hungary BIT (Article 2(2) and (3)) states that:

“2. Each Contracting Party shall accord in its territory to investments of the other Contracting Party and to investors with respect to their investments fair and equitable treatment and full protection and security in accordance with paragraphs 3 through 6.

3. 3. With respect to the investments the following measures or series of measures constitute breach of the obligation of fair and equitable treatment:

- a. denial of justice in criminal, civil or administrative proceedings; or*
- b. fundamental breach of due process, including a fundamental breach of transparency and obstacles to effective access to justice, in judicial and administrative proceedings; or*
- c. manifest arbitrariness; or*
- d. targeted discrimination on manifestly wrongful grounds, such as gender, race or religious belief; or*
- e. harassment, coercion, abuse of power or similar bad faith conduct.”*

The 2024 Uzbekistan-India BIT (Article 4.1) states that No Party shall subject investments made by investors of the other Party to measures which constitute a violation of customary international law (for greater certainty, it is clarified that “customary international law” only results from a general and consistent practice of States that they follow from a sense of legal obligation) through: (i) denial of justice in

¹⁸ For example, the 1998 Uzbekistan-Belgium-Luxembourg BIT, the 1993 Uzbekistan-France BIT, the 1992 Uzbekistan-Finland BIT, the 2004 Uzbekistan-Kuwait BIT, 2001 Uzbekistan-Sweden BIT, the 1994 Turkmenistan-France BIT, the 2002 Tajikistan-France BIT, the 2004 Tajikistan-Pakistan BIT, the 2003 Kyrgyzstan-Finland BIT, the 2004 Kyrgyzstan-France BIT, the 2016 Kyrgyzstan-Georgia BIT, the 2011 Kazakhstan-Estonia BIT, the 1998 Kazakhstan-France BIT, the 1997 Kazakhstan-Kuwait BIT

¹⁹ For example, the 2011 Uzbekistan-China BIT, the 2024 Uzbekistan-India BIT, the 2023 Turkmenistan-Hungary BIT, the 2024 Turkmenistan-Kazakhstan BIT, the 2024 Tajikistan-China BIT, the 2020 Kyrgyzstan-Hungary BIT, the 2019 Kyrgyzstan-India BIT, 2024 Kazakhstan-Kyrgyzstan BIT, the 2022 Kazakhstan-Qatar BIT, the 2018 Kazakhstan-Singapore BIT, the 2024 Kazakhstan-Turkmenistan BIT

any judicial or administrative proceedings; or (ii) fundamental breach of due process; or (iii) targeted discrimination on manifestly unjustified grounds, such as gender, race or religious belief; or (iv) manifestly abusive treatment, such as coercion, duress and harassment.”

The above-mentioned FET provisions allow to draw the following observations. First, the drafting of FET clauses spans a spectrum ranging from minimalist formulations to far more elaborate and precise ones, with a discernible trend toward states adopting increasingly detailed clauses. Second, these more elaborate formulations correspondingly narrow the interpretive latitude available to arbitral tribunals when applying the standard. This evolution may be understood as a deliberate response by states to the expansive interpretations of FET that unqualified clauses had tended to generate.

Why sweeping FET clauses are problematic?

The predominance of broad, unqualified FET clauses identified above is not a neutral drafting choice. Its consequences are structural, and they fall principally on the host state. Leaving the standard undefined gives rise to four interrelated difficulties: 1) the delegation of the standard’s normative content to arbitral tribunals; 2) its expansion through the doctrine of legitimate expectations; 3) the unpredictability generated by inconsistent awards; and 4) the chilling of legitimate regulation. Each of these is compounded by the asymmetric and costly architecture of investor-state arbitration, and each bears with particular force on the transition economies of Central Asia.

The first difficulty is one of indeterminacy. The terms “fair” and “equitable” are inherently open-textured, and an unqualified clause supplies no criterion by which their content may be ascertained that content has instead been left to develop through arbitral practice.²⁰ The practical effect is to transfer to tribunals a function that is, in substance, legislative since it is the arbitrators, rather than the contracting states, who determine after the event what conduct the standard prohibits. For states that negotiated no limiting language, this amounts to a significant and largely unintended

²⁰ Dolzer, Kriebaum and Schreuer. *Principles of International Investment Law*. 3rd Edition, Oxford University Press, 2022 – p.187-190

cession of regulatory authority to a body whose decisions they cannot anticipate and do not control.

The second and most consequential difficulty is the expansion of the standard through the doctrine of legitimate expectations. The history of investor-state dispute settlement shows that tribunals read into FET an obligation to provide a stable and predictable legal and business environment and to refrain from frustrating the expectations on the basis of which the investment was made. In its broadest form, this reasoning approaches a guarantee against regulatory change, converting FET into a de facto stabilisation clause to which the treaty parties never agreed. Although later tribunals, sought to balance investor expectations against the state's inherent right to regulate and cautioned that the standard must not become an insurance policy against ordinary legislative change, the breadth of an unqualified clause leaves ample room for the more expansive reading, and the outcome remains contingent on the composition of the particular tribunal.

The third difficulty is inconsistency. Investment arbitration knows no doctrine of binding precedent and is conducted by ad hoc tribunals. In the absence of a defined standard, materially similar facts have produced divergent outcomes. For a host state, the consequence is that compliance cannot be planned with confidence: the lawfulness of a measure under FET becomes knowable only after the event, and only once a particular tribunal has pronounced upon it. That unpredictability is itself in tension with the very rule-of-law values that the standard is said to vindicate.

The fourth difficulty is the chilling of legitimate regulation. Where the boundaries of the standard are unknown and the potential liability large, governments may defer, dilute or abandon measures in the public interest in order to avoid the risk of a claim, a phenomenon commonly described as regulatory chill. For the Central Asian states, which are transition economies engaged in the continuous reform of their legal and institutional frameworks, this constraint is especially serious, since the very process of legal modernisation that the region is undertaking is precisely the process most likely to disappoint an investor's asserted expectations.

These four difficulties are magnified by the asymmetric and costly architecture of

investor-state arbitration. FET is the most frequently invoked standard in investment claims, and among the most frequently successful, so that an unqualified clause translates directly into heightened exposure to awards of damages that may be substantial in relation to a developing state's fiscal capacity, quite apart from the considerable cost of defending the proceedings themselves. Taken together, these considerations explain why the unqualified FET clauses that dominate the treaty practice of Central Asia sit uneasily with the region's stated commitment to align investment protection with sustainable development, and why the recalibration of the standard, to which the discussion now turns, is warranted.

The reformation of FET in the BITs of Central Asia

In 2015 UNCTAD developed investment policy recommendations for sustainable development.²¹ One of the recommendations developed by UNCTAD included the reformation of FET clause in international investment agreements. In regard to qualification of the scope of FET, UNCTAD noted several options.

Several options exist to address the deficiencies of an unqualified FET standard, each with its pros and cons. The reference to customary international law may raise the threshold of State liability and help to preserve States' ability to adapt public policies in light of changing objectives (except when these measures constitute manifestly arbitrary conduct that amounts to egregious mistreatment of foreign investors). However, the exact contours of MST/CIL remain elusive. An option in this respect would be for the Parties to clarify their understanding of the standard by noting, for instance, that its breach requires an act that is an outrage, is made in bad faith, or constitutes a wilful neglect of duty or an insufficiency so far short of international standards that every reasonable and impartial person would readily recognize its insufficiency. This would confirm a high threshold for finding a breach of the standard. Another solution would be to replace the general FET clause with an exhaustive list of more specific obligations. While agreeing on such a list may turn out to be a challenging endeavour, its exhaustive nature would help avoid unanticipated

²¹ The 2015 UNCTAD Investment Policy Framework for Sustainable Development. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/investment-policy-framework-sustainable-development-2015-edition>
<https://www.europa-revue.com/index.php/eur>

and far-reaching interpretations by tribunals. The treaty could create a mechanism for periodic review of this exhaustive list by the Parties in order to keep it comprehensive and in line with developments in arbitral practice. A further option is to include FET as a political commitment (e.g. by mentioning it in the preamble only). On the one hand, this would come close to “omitting” FET, as the clause would not be legally binding, but only have best endeavour character. At the same time, if part of the preamble, FET language could give guidance for the interpretation of other treaty obligations. Finally, an omission of the FET clause would reduce States’ exposure to investor claims, but would also reduce the protective value of the agreement.²²

The current regulatory landscape of investment of Central Asian states indicate that the broad language of FET does not serve for sustainable development of the region.²³ Despite this, Central Asian states are attempting to incorporate sustainable development goals into the current regulatory framework. For example, the Model BIT developed for Uzbekistan, in co-operation with the ADB introduces significant deviations from Uzbekistan’s treaty practice to date, including limitation of the FET standard (Article 8). The model BIT restricts the ability of arbitral tribunals to provide a broad interpretation to the FET standard, clarifying that this refers only to a party’s obligation “not to deny justice to any investor in criminal, civil or administrative adjudicatory proceedings”. The model BIT also clarifies that the FET standard does not protect an investor’s legitimate expectations (e.g., on regulatory stability or the granting of permits).²⁴

The FET as reviewed for Central Asia

The foregoing analysis demonstrates that the treaty landscape of Central Asia remains dominated by unqualified, autonomous FET clauses that delegate an expansive and largely unchecked interpretive discretion to arbitral tribunals. If the standard is to be reconciled with the region’s sustainable-development objectives without depriving

²² The 2015 UNCTAD Investment Policy Framework for Sustainable Development, pp. 97-98. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/investment-policy-framework-sustainable-development-2015-edition>

²³ See, for example, the 2016 UNCTAD Investment Policy Review for Kyrgyzstan, p. 7-11. Available at: <https://unctad.org/publication/investment-policy-review-kyrgyzstan>

²⁴ The 2025 OECD Roadmap for Sustainable Investment Policy Reforms in Uzbekistan, p.166. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2025/11/roadmap-for-sustainable-investment-policy-reforms-in-uzbekistan_68204584.html

foreign investors of meaningful protection, two complementary reforms are recommended.

First, the FET clause should be confined to an exhaustive list of circumstances. Central Asian states should move away from open-textured, unqualified formulations and replace them with a provision that defines the standard exclusively by reference to a closed enumeration of the specific conduct capable of constituting a breach, for instance, denial of justice in judicial or administrative proceedings, a fundamental breach of due process, manifest arbitrariness, targeted discrimination on manifestly wrongful grounds, and harassment, coercion or other conduct amounting to bad faith. Unlike an indicative or illustrative list, an exhaustive list forecloses the residual discretion that has allowed tribunals to read additional and unanticipated elements, most notably a broad protection of investors' legitimate expectations, into the standard. The recent treaties surveyed above, including the 2023 Turkmenistan-Hungary BIT and the 2024 Uzbekistan-India BIT, already demonstrate that a closed enumeration is both workable.

Second, states should retain the capacity to review and revise the agreed limitations when needed. Because a closed list inevitably risks becoming outdated as arbitral practice evolves, each treaty should establish an institutional mechanism such as a joint committee of the contracting parties empowered to issue binding interpretations through which the parties may revisit the enumerated circumstances at defined intervals, or upon the request of either party, and amend them by mutual agreement. Such a review mechanism preserves the certainty and predictability that an exhaustive list affords, while ensuring that the standard remains responsive to legitimate developments in the law and is not, in the meantime, reopened to expansive judicial interpretation.

Third, states should clearly specify that the right of the state to regulate and adopt general regulatory changes do not constitute violations of FET standard. Such an explicit indication would allow to avoid any kind of external interpretation and assessment by arbitral tribunals whether a given measure amounted to the breach of FET standard.

Taken together, these measures would allow Central Asian states to retain the protective value of the FET standard while restoring to the contracting parties the control over its scope that unqualified clauses have hitherto ceded to arbitral tribunals.

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